
From Dargahs to Cinemas: Sufi Music's Journey into Hindi Film

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ABSTRACT

This research looks at how Sufi music has evolved over time, starting from its roots in dargahs (sufi shrines) to its incorporation into Bollywood film culture. Sufi music, which has been deeply affiliated with Islamic mysticism, has served as a powerful tool for demonstrating reverence for the divinity. When it entered the framework of Hindi cinema, this music underwent a metamorphosis, transforming from a dargah premise into a cultural and cinematic spectacle. The study aims at demonstrating the changes made to the Sufi themes, melodies, and lyrics so that they could be used in Hindi films and meet the expectation of a wider audience without significantly altering their spirituality. By examining critical film scores, composers, and songs, the study reveals the attempts made by Hindi cinema to shift the perception of Sufi music from something sacred towards popular consumption, which ultimately adds to the richness of Indian cinema. This highlights the continued relevance of Sufi music in contemporary narratives. Some of the highlights include: This research has shown how the deep spiritual roots and the powerful emotions embedded in Sufi music have fascinated Indian audiences from diverse religions, thus enriching the framework of Bollywood music.

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Introduction:

The universal love and compassion values enshrined in Sufi music have embraced various regions and religions through deep human and divine love. Today, Sufi music is a sought means of self-discovery and surrender to the almighty creator. For years now, Sufi music has been adopted into Hindi cinema, which has beautifully narrativized and culturally packaged it. The impact of Sufi songs in the Hindi cinema is indeed a remarkable blend of emotion, tradition, and modernity.

Methodology: The approach to the study is ethnographic and qualitative, having drawn on multiple disciplines like musicology, film studies, and cultural historiography to map the case of Sufi music's journey and transformation in Hindi cinema. It adopts a historical-literature review, text analysis of Hindi film songs, thematic analysis of the songs, and analysis of available interviews with the composers.

Focusing on each element of the definition, example or segment of Sufi music:

Over the years, Sufi music has emerged as the predominant form of Sufi expression, which is a mystical branch of Islam that first appeared in Persia, modern Iran, and later in South Asia around the 11th to 12th century.

It was the Sufi saints Jalaluddin, Bulleh Shah and Amir Khusru who created compelling spiritual and philosophical ideas through music and poetry.

Sufi Music remains distinctive with unchanging lyrical patterns and rhythm infused with emotions. Soft and hard instrumental accompaniment to Sufi music includes harmonium, tabla, and sitar. Qawwali is one of the well-known forms of music in Sufism. Qawwali captivates listeners by increasing the rhythm of the poetic expression of divine surrender and love. The human love counterpart and divine love are the primary themes dominating Sufi music. The melting away of egos shaped through mortal existence, longing to melt into union with the great creator lays the foundation for Sufi music.

Incorporation of Sufi Songs in Hindi Cinema

Hindi Cinema has used vast resources of Sufi music to weave into the plots and share cultural sentiments.

The impact of Sufi songs on Hindi cinema is a captivating mix of emotions and modern traditions. Between the 1940s and 1960s, Urdu poetry, Ghazals, and classical music had a strong impact on the Hindi film industry. Many of those songs bore an essence of Sufi music.

In 1960, *Barsat ki Raat* had remarkable qawwalis which included moving spiritual and romantic themes into the cinematic experience. This was the beginning of the experiment in Hindi cinema with Sufi music as a narrative device to elicit emotional or spiritual connection.

Period 1960s to 1980s

During this golden period of Hindi cinema, many well-known lyricists and composers emerged and fused Sufi elements into mainstream music. Nausad, Madan Mohan, and Khyyam produced Sufi inspired songs thematically and musically. During this period, the film *Mughal-e-Azam* (1960) featured Sufi inspired song 'Teri Mehfil mein' which centers on themes of Divine love and humanity. On the other hand the song 'parda hai parda' in the film 'Amar Akhbar Antony' (1977) is one of the remarkable examples of Sufi music, composed by Laxmikant-Pyarelal. This Qawwali bears the Sufi music tradition.

Contemporary Cinema and Restored Sufi Influence

The impact of globalization in the early 2000s resulted in Hindi cinema gaining international recognition, serving as a backdrop for the revival of Sufi music that was evident during this period. A.R. Rahman, one of the most celebrated film composers, played a key role in this revival. The Sufi musical influence was captured in A.R. Rahman's works 'Khawaja mere Khawaja' in the movie *Jodha Akaber* (2008) and 'Piya haji Ali' in the movie *Fida* (2000). His arrangements of traditional Sufi songs along with modern orchestration made them appealing to Indian and international audiences alike. Qawwalis have gained immense popularity among filmmakers due to their celebratory nature. In the film *My Name Is Khan* (2010), Shankar-Ehsaan-Loy celebrated faith, devotion, and humanity in the track 'Noor-e-Khuda.' Pritam also composed the lāla Bajan gi bhaja Shranggi' (2015), which further added to the growing popularity of Qawwalis in Hindi cinema. Mithun also composed popular track 'Maula mere maula' which featured in *Anwar* (2007).

Apart from this, a contemporary development in Hindi films is the inclusion of Sufi rock and its integration in modern Bollywood pop music. It was popularized by singers like Kailash Kher.

These kinds of songs such as “Allah ke bande” uses modern Sufi rock inspiration, merging spiritual essence into a rock format.

Contribution of Sufi songs in themes of Hindi Cinema

The idea of love as a road that leads to God is the primary theme in Sufi music. Usually, Shufis fight for romantic storylines and graph them into abstract ideas and themes in Hindi cinema which is based on the central idea of Sufi music. The way song ‘Kun faya kun’ in the movie Rockstar 2011 encapsulated love and presented it as a feeling of revelation and awakening. On the other hand, the song ‘Arziya’ in the movie Delhi 6 (2009) used poetic imagery to juxtapose personal love with devotion to show the multilayered narrative on an emotional and spiritual level.

In the movie ‘Rab ne bana di Jodi’ (2008), the song ‘tujh me rab dikhta hai’ also depicts sufi way of love where he portrays the beloved as the image of God.

Many Hindi films have used Sufi music to portray the inner conflicts and the quest of the character in the film.

As illustrated in the film ‘Rockstar’, the protagonist's longing is captured in the song ‘Kun faya kun’. The song has become a means of self-reflection and a way to communicate with God.

The place of Sufi music in Hindi cinema- Sufi music is part of Sufi Hindi cinema which reflects the rich syncretic nature of the diverse traditions, religions, and cultures of India. By integrating Sufi music into Hindi cinema, it pays tribute to Islamic cultural heritage and connects modernity with tradition.

Sufi traditions Hindi cinema adopted have promoted the art form internationally. Especially A. R. Rahman’s modern orchestration of Sufi inspired music gained global recognition.

Challenges and Criticisms

Despite the immense success regarding the use of music in Bollywood films, this process goes through harsh criticism. Detractors argue that the commercialization of Sufi songs into popular cuisine with modern background music has destroyed the spirit of Sufi music.

Alongside this, the application of Sufi elements in certain films has turned deep philosophical traditions into a superficial aesthetic device. Finding the balance between authenticity and creativity is a problem for filmmakers and composers.

Conclusion

It is appreciated in Sufi music's integration in the context of Hindi cinema because it shows its depth and cultural richness. The love, devotion, and reverence encapsulated in the Sufi music touches listeners profoundly, adds to the storyline, and yields an intriguing experience. Sufi music should be sought after and incorporated into further projects in Hindi cinema, always keeping in mind the cultural and spiritual foundations of the Sufi traditions. The essence of Sufi music's praise and interconnection with Hindi cinema can be maintained through respecting their traditions. The widespread acceptance of Sufi songs in Hindi cinema alongside other genres has revitalized interest in such folk music. Many contemporary and emerging artists have taken Sufi music and blended the essence of Sufi music with modern genres to create innovative compositions.

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